

Environmental vibrations due to installation at high frequency

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ABSTRACT

Traditional vibrators sheet piles and foundation piles work at 25-40 Hz, but recently vibrators with very high frequency are developed; A so-called resonator has frequency about 120-150 Hz. The paper presents field measurement and the modelling of the environmental vibrations. Two cases will be discussed: installation of wooden piles with a traditional vibrator in clay layer over sand and installation of sheet piles with a resonator in a sandy soil

For both cases vibrations are measured at the surface at several distances. The measurements are presented with focus on the decay of amplitude with distance. Empirical decay curves are derived and compared.

A numerical model for the source and wave propagation is discussed. The source model is based on the CPT-results (shaft friction and cone resistance) together with a dynamical factor. The wave propagation in the surrounding soil is based on a semi-analytical method for layered soil, with integration over the embedded length of the element. The results are compared with the results of the measurements.

The model will be used to analyze the consequences of the vibration frequency on environmental vibrations. The importance of pile length and toe resistance can be derived. The strength of the vibrations with depth might differ strongly from the vibrations at surface.

The question whether the regulations for vibrations in structures must be extended is raised.

Keywords: vibratory driving, resonator, field measurement, numerical model

1 INTRODUCTION

Vibratory driving of sheet piles and foundation piles is an efficient installation method. Often application is not allowed due to high environmental vibrations in neighboring buildings. Traditional vibrators work at 25-40 Hz, but vibrators with very high frequency are developed (1), but recently application in the Netherlands has started. A so-called resonator has frequency about 120-150 Hz. The drivability of a pile is of interest, see e.g. (2). This paper focusses on the environmental vibrations of vibratory hammers, to get an answer on the question whether such high frequency hammers may lead to a reduction of environmental vibrations.

2 MODEL DESCRIPTION

The numerical model contains two parts: a source and wave propagation model. The two models are coupled by integration over the full length of the sheet pile.

The source model is based on the CPT-results (shaft friction and cone resistance) together with a dynamical factor. In this paper all forces along the pile are assumed to be fully in phase. To take fatigue of the

soil into account, the dynamic factor may depend on the position of the source point above the pile toe.

The wave propagation in the surrounding soil is based on a semi-analytical method for layered soil (1), called Scatmat. Scatmat assumes a horizontally layered linear elastic soil under axial symmetry. The model is based on the scattering matrix method: for each homogeneous layer upward and downward waves are considered, where the solution is calculated from the continuity of velocity and stress at the interfaces. Due to a numerical limitation, the number of interfaces between the source and the receivers is limited, which limits the number of layers added to this model.

The influence of all forces is summed over depth. The result is calculated for a unit Ricker wavelet as input force in time. The result in the time domain of both the load and the calculated accelerations are transformed to the frequency domain by FFT. From the transfer together with the value of the dynamic soil resistance the result for all frequencies is calculated. Finally, an average over a limited frequency range around the vibration frequency gives the desired acceleration. The vibration velocity is calculated by division by (angular) frequency.

3 FIELD MEASUREMENTS

The model is calibrated by the results of two measurements. The data for the cases are summarized in Table 1 in the Appendix at the end of the paper.

The measurements are processed to get the highest value at a location during installation of a (sheet) pile. This maximum is not always found at the deepest position of the pile.

3.1 Traditional vibrator 50 Hz

The vibrations during of installation of many wooden piles with a traditional vibrator in clay layer over sand has been measured. The site was nearby Delfgauw, East of Delft. The installation consists of two phases: first the wooden pile length was installed in a predrilled hole and vibrated over a few meters. Next a concrete set-up was installed. The accelerations were measured with a smartphone, with sample frequency around 100 Hz. So, the vibration frequency is close to the Nyquist frequency. By placing the smartphone for each pile at known distance, for many piles an idea of the average acceleration level with distance is found.

Fig. 1 shows the measured accelerations on distance, both on logarithmic scale, together with the trend lines. The measured acceleration is inverse proportional to the distance to the pile.

The amplitude on distance is described by a power law

$$\frac{v(r)}{v(r_{ref})} = \left(\frac{r}{r_{ref}} \right)^{-n}$$

with r distance to the source [m], r_{ref} reference distance [5 m], v vibration velocity [mm/s] and n empirical power [-].

For this case the value $n = 0.9-1.3$ and the reference vertical velocity $v_{ref} = 1.4$ mm/s at $r_{ref} = 5$ m, assuming a harmonic motion of 50 Hz. The horizontal velocity is smaller.

Fig. 1 Measured maximum accelerations in Vriezenveen. Each symbol refers to one sheet pile. Since the transducers were not replaced, the distance between the transducers and the sheet piles is different for each sheet pile.

3.2 Resonator 150 Hz

Near the village of Vriezenveen, North of Almelo, in the East of the Netherlands, the existing quay-wall must be replaced. To avoid damage of nearby structures, a test with a so-called Resonator (4) was carried out. The principle is to bring the sheet pile to a resonance state, leading to a high displacement at the pile toe. In this case the resonance frequency was about 150 Hz. In general, this frequency decreases with length of the sheet pile. The exact value depends on soil resistance too.

The sheet piles AZ 18/700 length 11 m were installed at the water side of the existing quay-wall, the water depth is a about 2 m. The subsoil is mainly sand, with a thin peat layer. Along the channel is a minor road, that was closed during the measurements.

The measurement was carried out by 4 2D Sundstrand accelerometers at four points A-D at distances 2.4, 8.6, 12.7 and 17.0 m from the sheet wall. The road is between the measurement points A and B). The horizontal direction is perpendicular to the sheet pile wall. Here 1 kHz sample frequency was used. In this paper only results from installing single sheet piles is considered. 11 single sheet piles are installed. The accelerations are integrated with respect to time to obtain the velocity.

Fig. 2 Measured vertical velocity [mm/s] on time [s] at locations A (top) to D (bottom).

Fig. 2 shows the vertical velocity on time. The total installation time of the sheet pile is about 7.5 min, resulting in an average speed of 1.4 m/min. Also visible

is the fact that the extreme values at each location is reached at different times, suggesting that interference plays an important role in the soil response. A strong decay of maximum vibration level with distance is visible in the results.

Fig. 3 Measured maximum accelerations in Delfgauw. The numbers show the acceleration at distance $x = 0$ m and the slope of the trendline.

Fig. 3 shows the velocities that are measured on double logarithmic scale.

For this case the value $n = 1.65$ and the reference velocity $v_{ref} = 1.32$ mm/s at $r_{ref} = 5$ m. The vertical vibration within 6 m from the sheet pile is almost constant. The power n is higher than the Delfgauw case, and the reference velocity is comparable. The horizontal velocity is higher than the vertical velocity.

4 MODEL APPLICATION

4.1 Traditional vibrator 50 Hz

The situation is modelled. Table 2 shows the properties. Two cases are calculated, with and without set-up. The setup is introduced by an adjustment of the shaft friction along the set-up: the friction is doubled and at the end (1.3 m) the value is based on the cone resistance. Since the set-up has a higher area, the dynamic factor reduces compared with the model without the dynamic factor, to get results that are comparable with the measured values.

Fig. 4 shows the comparison with the measured values. The calculated horizontal acceleration is far too low. This suggests that this aspect is not properly considered in the model, maybe the out of plane motion

of the pile (due to bending) plays a role. The set-up has influence on the calibration of the dynamic factor, and the fit on the dominant vertical vibration improves slightly.

Fig. 4 Measured and simulated accelerations on distance case Delfgauw.

4.2 Resonator 150 Hz

The AZ 18/700 sheet pile (5) has a painted area of 1.86 m², leading to an equivalent diameter of 0.59 m. The accelerations are calculated at five distances, equal to the distances from the measurement points Points A D, where one point between A and B at 4.5 m from the sheet pile wall has been added.

The vibrations are calculated for a dynamical factor of 0.167 and a fatigue described by $\exp(-\alpha \cdot (L-z))$, with α the fatigue factor (0.4 m⁻¹) L the embedded length of the pile (11 m) and z the depths of the cross-section.

Fig. 5 Calculated vibration velocity on distance for case Vriezenveen, influence of damping

Fig. 5 shows the calculated vibrations for damping 1%, 4% and 6%, together with the fit for measured vibrations. The calculated decay on distance is clearly underestimated.

4.3 The background of variations

The reason for this difference is because the decay of maximum values during installation differs from the decay at one moment (i.e. position of the sheet pile). This can be seen in Fig. 2. The numerical model shows similar behavior. Fig. 6 shows the calculated maximum

values for five depths of the pile toe. The vibration velocity is presented on logarithmic scale to show also details for the points farther away. The calculated points are formally realizations of time points in Fig. 2, where one should take into account that the depth and time are not similar, since penetration rate may depend on depth. In Fig. 6 the variation of maximum velocity at one distance with penetration depth of the pile toe is visible. The penetration depth is the depth of the pile toe and, therefore, the (embedded) length where the shaft friction occurs (apart from the fact that the first 2 m is in the water and, therefore, has no shaft friction. Remarkable is the fact that the maximum velocity close to the pile (point A at 2.4 m) decreases with penetration depth, while far away from the pile (point D at 17 m) the maximum velocity increases with penetration depth.

Fig. 6 Maximum vibration velocity on penetration depth for case Vriezenveen

The sensitivity of the vibration level to frequency and distance is shown by Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, where for all frequencies the transfer to the 5 points at the surface is shown for penetration depth 10 m and 9 m respectively. For all frequencies the dynamic factors are identical. The strange behaviour at 30 Hz is a numerical irregularity, caused by zero energy in the source spectrum.

For the frequency 150 Hz in the points nearby, a clear difference between the vibration level with penetration depth is seen. E.g. the two nearby points: at penetration level 9 m (Fig. 7) the velocity in the points at 2.4 and 4.5 m differs about 30%, while at penetration level 10 m (Fig. 8) the velocity is almost equal.

In general, it is interesting to note that these figures reveal typical and quite strong wave interference patterns for frequencies above 120 Hz for horizontal vibrations and between 50 and 130 Hz for vertical vibrations.

Fig. 7 Case Vriezenveen: transfer for penetration depth 9 m

Fig. 8 Case Vriezenveen: transfer for penetration depth 10 m

4.4 Vibrations on depth

The numerical model offers the possibility to compare the vibration levels at surface and depth.

Fig. 9 compares the vibrations at surface level (upper graph) and at 5 m depth (lower graph). The vertical vibrations close to the pile are comparable for both depths, but the decay with distance at depth is much higher. The horizontal vibrations at depth 5 m are much higher. Despite the higher decay at depth, the horizontal acceleration is higher than at surface over the full distance range that is considered. For structures with a foundation at this level, usage of the vibrations at surface may lead to erroneous results.

5 CONSEQUENCES FOR STRUCTURES

The resonator leads to comparable vibration loading as traditional vibrators in the nearfield but with a much higher decay rate with distance. This is an important aspect for application in urban areas. If a structure is nearby the installation works, the structure is loaded by a high frequency being 120-150 Hz.

Fig. 9 Comparison vibrations at surface (top) and at 5 m depth (bottom) in case Vriezenveen penetration depth 11 m. Dynamic factors are 0.1.

In the Dutch vibration guidelines (6) the frequencies above 100 Hz maybe filtered from the measured signals. This means that according to the guidelines these frequencies are always allowed. The background of this filtering might have a signal processing background. The sensitivity of (elements of) structures for frequencies above 100 Hz must be evaluated before these frequencies can be applied with confidence.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Measurements show that a resonator that works at 150 Hz leads to lower environmental vibrations, where especially the decay with distance is higher.

The phenomenon is modelled by a source and semi-analytical propagation model. The model doesn't recover the correct decay with distance for a single pile, showing that the decay rate of maximum values during installation differs from the decay at one moment of installation.

The horizontal vibrations are poorly described by this model. An explanation for this difference might be the vibrations from horizontal motion in the pile during installation. This requires an extension of the model with horizontal forces.

The shaft friction in the sand seems to be reduced by the high frequency.

The model suggests that at larger depths the vibrations might differ strongly from the vibrations at the surface.

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APPENDIX: DATA FOR THE CASES

Table 1 Properties of elements and equipment

Location	Delfgauw	Vriezenveen
Element	timber pile	steel sheet pile
Specification	with set up	AZ 18/700
Length [m]	13	11
Diameter [m]	0.1/0.2	0.59
Length set-up [m]	1.3	-
Diameter set-up [m]	0.4	-
Vibrator [Hz]	50	150

Table 2 Properties soil Delfgauw

Material	clay	sand
Thickness [m]	12	4
cone resistance [MPa]	0.35	8
shaft friction [MPa]	0.01	0.056
Volume weight [kN/m ³]	14	20
Shear modulus [MN/m ²]	7.81	85.9
Bulk modulus [MN/m ²]	75.5	401
Poisson ration [-]	0.45	0.40

Table 3 Properties soil Vriezenveen

Material	sand	sand	sand
Thickness [m]	1.2	0.7	∞
cone resistance [MPa]	0	0	8
shaft friction [MPa]	0	0	0.08
Volume weight [kN/m ³]	18	20	20
Shear modulus [MN/m ²]	22	60.3	67.5
Bulk modulus [MN/m ²]	132	362	280
Poisson ration [-]	0.40	0.40	0.40

